

Chelating Tendencies of Ferron with Some Metal Ions

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Ferron, 7-iodo 8-hydroxy quinoline 5-sulphonic acid is a well known chelating agent forming a number of chelates with different metal ions. Dagmar, Jokelleova¹ used it for the spectrophotometric determination of aluminium in the presence of iron. Ekman and Nasanen² determined the stability constants of Ca^{+2} both potentiometrically and spectrophotometrically. Vusitalo³ studied the thermodynamics of the formation of Mg chelates. Earlier, complexes of ferron with Cu^{+2} , Ni^{+2} , Co^{+2} , Mn^{+2} , Zn^{+2} were studied⁴, but no work seems to have been done on Be^{+2} , Al^{+3} and Cr^{+3} chelates. Hence the present work was undertaken with a view to study the stoichiometry and stepwise formation constants of these chelates using a potentiometric method.

The experimental method consisted of pH titrations of the free ligand, in the absence of and in the presence of metal ion under investigation. The ionic strength was maintained constant by using a medium containing 0.1M KNO_3 in low concentration ($1.0 \times 10^{-3}M$) of the ligand and the metal ion. The pH titrations were carried out by introducing free ligand as well 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 ratios of metal ion to ligand concentration in a titration cell. The cell was a double walled glass vessel through which water was circulated at a constant temperature from a thermostat. The pH readings were taken after the addition of small increments of 0.1M carbon dioxide free KOH solution. The chemicals employed were of AnalaR grade. Beryllium nitrate E.M. (extra pure) sample was dissolved in double distilled water and the solution was standardised gravimetrically as Beryllium phosphate⁵. Sodium salt of 7-iodo 8-hydroxy quinoline 5-sulphonic acid was used. An Elico pH meter Model LI-10 with Beckman glass and calomel electrode was employed for the pH measurements. The pH meter was standardised using standard Buffer of potassium hydrogen phthalate.

The determination of stoichiometry by monovariation method⁶ has shown the existence of 1 : 1 of Cr^{+3} chelate and 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 chelates of Be^{+2} , Mg^{+2} , Ca^{+2} and Al^{+3} .

The first and second chelate stability constants were calculated from 1 : 2 titration curves by an adoption of Bjerrums method followed by Calvin and Wilson⁷, employing the final equation.

1. Dagmar, Jokelleova, *C.A.*, 1967, **61**, 101327e.
2. A. Ekman and R. Nasanen, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1953, **7**, 1261.
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7. M. Calvin and K. W. Wilson, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, **67**, 2003.

$$\bar{n} = \frac{1}{C_M} [aC_A + H^+ - [A] - A^-]$$

C_M = total concentration of metal ion.

C_A = total concentration of the ligand.

$[A]$ = original HNO_3 added.

a = equivalents of alkali added per mole of the ligand and A^- was calculated by the use of the following equation.

$$A^- = \frac{pK_1}{H^+} [C_A + A - aC_A + H^+]$$

The pK_1 for ferron has been taken⁴ as 7.04.

The values of pK_1 and pK_2 at 28° calculated by the above equation for different metal ions is shown in Table-I.

TABLE I

Sl. No.	Metal ion	8-hydroxy 7-iodoquinoline 5-sulphonic acid			8-hydroxy quinoline 5-sulphonic acid	
		pK_1	pK_2	K_1K_2	pK_1	pK_2
1.	Be^{+2}	4.65	5.25	9.90	—	—
2.	Mg^{+2}	3.25	3.95	7.20	4.79	8.2
3.	Ca^{+2}	2.60	—	—	3.52	—
4.	Al^{+3}	6.76	7.00	13.77	—	—
5.	Cr^{+3}	5.48	—	—	—	—

The value of pK_1 for Ca-ferron obtained in the present investigation agreed favourably well with a value obtained by Ekman and Nasanen². It was not possible to calculate the pK_2 for Ca^{+2} since \bar{n} values do not go higher than 0.60. It is evident from the above data that the relative values of stabilities with ferron follow the order $Be^{+2} > Mg^{+2} > Ca^{+2}$. The Al^{+3} and Cr^{+3} ferron chelates are more stable because of their smaller ionic radii. A plot of pK_1 of the above metal ion=ferron chelates against the Z^2/r_m yields a straight line with the exception of Be^{+2} . K_1, K_2 values of 8-hydroxyquinoline 5-sulphonic acid for Mg^{+2} , Ca^{+2} is higher than that of ferron-chelates. This is understandable since the basicity of the ferron is less than that of 8-hydroxy quinoline 5-sulphonic acid and hence its lower stability constant.

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